

Bush Induction Heating

Maximum excitation current, I_{max} : 50 A

Frequency, f : 75 kHz

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Revision history

Revision	Date	Comment
0.3	2024-04-30	Final revision.
0.2	2023-11-22 WED	Add 6 turn coil for small bush, flat spiral 2 turns, core iron co-axial
0.1	2023-11-17 FRI	Initial revision.

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Acronyms

Not relevant in this report so far.

1. Introduction

The bush being considered have dimension and designation as in in Table 1. The dimensions are displayed in the schema of Figure 1.

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Table 1 Size of the bushes considered in this study.

designation	10--f-km	12--f-km	13-___fakm
A_max_OD	14.029	16.029	30.035
B_Min_OD	14.018	16.018	30.022
G_Max_ID	10.027	12.033	25.04
H_Min_ID	10.005	12.006	25.007
A_width_incl_flange	12	12	24.75
C_Flange_width_stem	1.5	1.5	1.4375
E_OD_Flange	16	22	34.875
D_Bore_ID	11.027	13.033	27.024

Figure 1 Schema of the bush dimensions.

2. Bush temperature

The temperature field in stationary regime is considered for the bushes of three sizes: small size, i.e., 10--f-km, medium size, i.e., 12--f-km, large size, i.e., 13-___fakm. It is noticed that the hottest

region is in flange area for each of the three bush sizes, see Figure 2, Figure 4 and Figure 6. Cross

sections of the bushes allows a better appreciation of the temperature gradients for each of the three bush sizes, see Figure 3, Figure 5 and Figure 7. When the size of the bush is smaller, the air gap to the coil is larger. The effect of this larger gap is increasing the maximum temperature that the bush reaches, which ranges from 135.93 C to 152.29 C to 176,27 C for the small, medium, and large sizes respectively. The range of the temperatures is 135.86 – 135.93 C for the small bush, 152.04 – 152.29 C for the medium size bush and 175.42 – 176.26 C for the large bush. The Study of the temperature increment during the first 240 second from the activation of the excitation current in the coils is provided in three separate video. The temperature shown here are in stationary regime, i.e., when an equilibrium is reached in the balance of power the heat the bush and the power that is radiate by the bush hot surfaces. Because of this equilibrium of power, the temperature remain constant.

3. Volumetric Electric power density losses

As it is observed in Figure 8, Figure 9 and Figure 10 the maximum of the volumetric power loss in W/

is increasing from 56.7 to 85.7 to 288 when considering bushes of larger size in the same coil size.

Although the maximum is increasing, the figures do not show a noticeable change of the Power density losses on average. That means that the power loss that is translated into heating power in the bush might be larger in some areas of the bush the thicker the air gap coil-bush is. Yet, on average this is scarcely visible in a bush cross section. The frequency of 75 kHz used focuses the losses, hence the heating power generation in a very thin layer around the surfaces of the bush.

4. Field of the Magnetic flux density norm $||\mathbf{B}||$

In Figure 11, Figure 12 and Figure 13 it is noticed that the norm of the magnetic flux density $||\mathbf{B}||$ is higher in the air gap between the turn of a coil and the bush. This suggests that, if the turns are closely packed a higher norm of the magnetic flux density \mathbf{B} can be obtained more uniformly inside the coil. Also, the Norm is visibly increasing the smaller is the air space between the bush and the coil. The maximum of the magnetic flux density norm $||\mathbf{B}||$ is increasing from 11.8 to 12.2 to 23.8 mT (milli Tesla) when the bush inserted into the same coil is of small, medium and large size, respectively.

5. Doubling the numbers of turns for the small bush

By adding 3 additional turns for a total of 6 turns in the excitation coil, the temperature of the bush approximately double, see Figure 14 Temperature of the small bush and the coil for a 6-turn coil. - Figure 3. The power loss in the bush and in the coil also double, see Figure 15 - Figure 8 and Figure 16- Figure 11.

The inner turns of the coils are hotter than the external turns. The central external turn is colder than the other two external turns.

The bush reaches a temperature of 249 C. Judging by the colour scale, the coil turns are in the range 140-180 C ca.

6. Two-turn flat spiral and small bush

The small bush was placed on a small 2-turns flat coil, i.e., a spiral. The temperature of the bush and the turns of the coils are displayed in Figure 17. The Magnitude of the magnetic field density B is higher in the centre of the flat coil spiral and between its turns. By looking at the colour scale, it is less than 10 mT elsewhere. This spiral seems a less favourable set-up than the 3-turn coil of Figure 11. The bush reaches about 69 C uniformly with the spiral and 135 C with the 3-turn vertical coil of Figure 3.

7. Using an iron core to transfer the magnetic flux density to the bush

A not-laminated iron core has been placed inside a 3-turn coil and the small bush. No hysteresis has been modelled for simplicity. Relative permeability was kept constant at 4,000, as in the default. The coil and the bush are set coaxially far apart. The bush remains at 20 C ca, while the rod heats up to 500 C ca., see Figure 19.

8. Coil concatenated with the small bush

The coil geometry was obtained as an instance of the ‘Single Conductor Coil – Generic’ member of the ‘Geometry Parts library. The parameters are displayed in Table 2 . The resulting geometry is displayed in Figure 20. The current amplitude and frequency are kept constant at 50 A and 75 kHz, respectively. The only heat transfer from the boundaries of the coil and of the bush is assumed to be by radiation, with an emissivity surface coefficient of 0.8. This assumption has been made following a case presented in the COMSOL video tutorial [Modeling Inductive Heating in a Coil Using COMSOL Multiphysics®](#) .

With a one-turn coil the bush remains at 20 C, whereas the coils reaches 102 C. The only change occurring by considering a one-turn coil is that the coil reaches 102 C, whereas the bush remains cool at 20 C. These results were obtained with a box air domain and imposing a air conductivity of 1

Table 2 Instance parameters of the 'Single Conductor Coil – Generic' in the COMSOL 'Geometry Parts' library.

coil_chirality 0	"Coil chirality: 1-Left handed, 0-Right handed".
coil_depth 17[mm]	"Coil inner depth (bobbin depth)"
coil_fillet 2.5[mm]	"Coil inner fillet (bobbin fillet)"
coil_height 8[mm]	"Coil height (0 for compacted coil)"
coil_width 35[mm]	"Coil inner width (bobbin width)"
connection_type 0	"Connection type: 6-Open helix, 5-Closed hoops, 4-Open side, 3-Closed side, 2-Open corner, 1-Closed corner, 0-No connection"
eff_wire_height 2[mm]	"Effective wire cross section height (to make thin turns behave like thick turns)"
eff_wire_width 2[mm]	"Effective wire cross section width (to make thin turns behave like thick turns)"
no_turns 2	"Number of turns (noninteger for connection type 6, integer otherwise)"
partitioning 0	"Partitioning faces (relevant for connection type 5): 1-Include, 0-Exclude"
tolerance 1e-3	"Smallest supported feature size, relative to coil size"
wire_fillet 1[mm]	"Wire cross section fillet (0 for sharp corners)"
wire_height 2[mm]	"Wire cross section height (0 for boundary coil)"
wire_width 2[mm]	"Wire cross section width (0 for boundary coil)"

S/m, as suggested in the COMSOL video tutorial [Modeling Transformers and Inductors in COMSOL Multiphysics®](#) .

A second coil geometry was then tested where a three-turn winding close to the bush is examined. The Figure 23 shows that the bush still remains at 20 C, the coil reaches 49.7 C. The COMSOL video tutorial [Modeling Inductive Heating in a Coil Using COMSOL Multiphysics®](#) suggests using a spherical air domain with a layer that is assigned an “Infinite Element domain” definition. Conductivity of the air domain is kept at its default 0 S/m value. Following these suggestions, a second analysis was conducted. In Figure 24, the resulting bush and coil temperatures are inferred by the colour scale. The bush remains cool at 20 C, whereas the coil reaches 46.6 C. These values appear in good agreement with those obtained with slightly conductive box-shaped air domain, considered earlier.

Figure 23 Concatenated coil, small bush, 50 A, 75 kHz, narrow winding box air domain 1 S/m.

9. Matrix of design performance

Bush size	Small	Medium	Large
Conc-1: coil parallel to bush axis, 2D	X	X	X
Conc-2: coil orthogonal to bush axis			
Conc-4: coil with turns inside bush	X		

References

- [1] NASA, "Pluto: The 'other' red planet," <https://www.nasa.gov/nh/pluto-the-other-red-planet>, 2015, accessed: 2018-12-06.